

AI Based Career Pathway Recommendation System for IT Undergraduates

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Abstract

Many IT undergraduates in Sri Lanka face challenges in selecting career pathways that align with their skills, interests, and academic backgrounds. Existing career guidance services are often generic, lack personalization, and fail to reflect the evolving local IT job market. This research aimed to address these gaps by developing CareerGuru an AI-based career pathway recommendation system tailored specifically for IT undergraduates. Using the Design Science Research (DSR) methodology, data were collected through interviews with students and career advisors to identify challenges and system requirements. The system integrates the Big Five personality model, the RIASEC career interest framework, skill assessments, and CV parsing to build comprehensive user profiles. These are analyzed using the OpenAI ChatGPT API to produce personalized, explainable career recommendations, skill-gap identification, and learning resource suggestions. CareerGuru was developed as a web-based platform using HTML, CSS, and JavaScript for the frontend, Node.js for the backend, and OpenAI's ChatGPT API for AI processing. The platform supports CV uploads in PDF/DOCX formats and generates a downloadable Career Insight Report containing recommended IT roles aligned with the Sri Lankan market. Pilot testing with IT undergraduates and expert validation by career advisors confirmed that the system delivers relevant, actionable, and locally contextualized recommendations. CareerGuru enhances early career planning, improves decision-making confidence, and bridges the gap between academic preparation and industry needs. Future enhancements include university-wide deployment, multilingual support, advanced machine learning-based predictions, and integration with online learning platforms.

Keywords: *Artificial Intelligence, Career Guidance, IT Undergraduates, Big Five Personality, Generative Artificial Intelligence, Career Recommendation System*